

Studies on the Polarographic Maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-Nitrophenols and Their Suppression by Some Ionic and Non-ionic Surfactants

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Role of some ionic and non-ionic surfactants in the suppression of polarographic negative maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols (in 4% ethanolic solution) has been studied at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in BR buffer of pH 6.09. It is observed that all types of surfactants (cationic, anionic and non-ionic) suppress these maxima, the cationic ones being the most effective. Their characteristic properties, viz., maximum suppression point (M. S. P.), specific suppression coefficient (S. S. C.) and critical micelle concentration (C. M. C.) have been determined. On the basis of (M. S. P.) values, the order of relative efficacies of cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactants in the suppression of the negative maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols has been established.

NITRO compounds exhibit maxima in their reduction waves¹. However, studies relating to the effect of ionic and non-ionic surfactants on these maxima are sparse. Lal and Srivastava² have studied the effect of some ionic and non-ionic surfactants on the maxima of nitrobenzene. Recently, Ram and Singh³ have studied the effect of some ionic and non-ionic surfactants on the suppression of the maxima of nitrotoluenes. So far as the appearance and suppression of the maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols is concerned, no study has been reported so far. This paper deals with the study on the suppression of the maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols by some ionic and non-ionic surfactants.

Experimental

O-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols were BDH products of high purity and were recrystallised from ethanol before use. Other chemicals used were of AR BDH grade. The surfactants used were also of high purity. The concentration of each of the depolarizers in the solution to be polarographed was maintained at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ (in 4% ethanolic solution containing appropriate amounts of the constituents of BR buffer of pH 6.09, which also acted as a supporting electrolyte).

A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CLO2) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal PL 50) was used. All measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified nitrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.). The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1M KCl, open circuit) : $h_{\text{corr}} = 62.4 \text{ cm}$; $m = 3.12 \text{ mg/sec}$; $t = 2.60 \text{ sec}$; $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.504 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/6}$.

The number of electrons (*n*) involved in the reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon⁴. This gave the value of *n* equal to 6 in the case of *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols and 4 in the case of *m*-nitrophenol at pH 6.09.

The following surfactants were used :

Cationic : Lauryl pyridinium chloride (LPC), Cetyl pyridinium chloride (CPC), Cetyl pyridinium bromide (CPB), Cetyl dimethyl benzyl ammonium chloride (CDBAC) and Cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB).

Anionic : Dodecyl benzene sulphonate (DBS), Sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), Tergitol-7, Manoxol-OT and Manoxol-IB.

Non-ionic : Triton X-100, Gelatin, Decon-90, Ethyl digol and 2-Ethoxy ethanol.

Results and Discussion

Representative Figs. 1(a), (b), (c) depict the morphology of C-V curves of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols in the presence of increasing concentrations of the surfactants.

O-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols under the chosen experimental conditions yield sharp maxima which lie at $-0.58V$, $-0.61V$ and $-0.65V$ (vs S.C.E.) respectively from the potential of the electrocapillary zero, which is $-0.32V$ (S.C.E.) under the same experimental conditions. Thus, the maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols lie on the negative side of the electrocapillary zero and hence these are of negative polarity⁵.

Under the same experimental conditions the relative heights of the maxima are in the following order :

o-nitrophenol > *p*-nitrophenol > *m*-nitrophenol

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Fig. 1. (a): Polarograms of *o*-nitrophenol in the presence of increasing concentration of LPC
 (i) 0.0 M; (ii) 2×10^{-6} M; (iii) 7×10^{-6} M; (iv) 1×10^{-5} M; (v) 2×10^{-5} M; (vi) 3×10^{-5} M
 (b): Polarograms of *m*-nitrophenol in the presence of increasing concentration of LPC
 (i) 0.0 M; (ii) 5.0×10^{-6} M; (iii) 8.0×10^{-6} M; (iv) 1.0×10^{-5} M; (v) 1.5×10^{-5} M; (vi) 2.8×10^{-5} M
 (c): Polarograms of *p*-nitrophenol in the presence of increasing concentration of LPC
 (i) 0.0 M; (ii) 5.0×10^{-6} M; (iii) 8.0×10^{-6} M; (iv) 1.0×10^{-5} M; (v) 1.4×10^{-5} M; (vi) 2.0×10^{-5} M

Effect of increasing concentrations of the surfactants on the maxima: The effect of increasing concentrations of cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactants on E_{max} and i_{max} has been studied and the values are listed in Table 1. A perusal of this table reveals that E_{max} of all the three maxima gets shifted to less negative potentials (positive shift) as the concentration of cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactants is increased.

The decrease in the value of i_{max} from the stage when no surfactant is present to the point just preceding the elimination of the maxima is different for the three isomers. The decrease in i_{max} is in the following order:

After the suppression of the maxima by requisite amounts of the surfactants, each depolarizer yields a well-defined wave [Figs. 1 a(vi), b(vi), c(vi)], which is diffusion-controlled and irreversible.

Characteristic properties of surfactants vis-a-vis their relative efficacies in the suppression of the maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols: The values of characteristic properties viz., M.S.P., S.S.C. and C.M.C. of the surfactants in respect of the maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols were determined⁶⁻⁸ and have been listed in Table 2. A perusal of this table reveals that M.S.P., S. S. C. and C.M.C. values for cationic surfactants are much less than those for anionic ones. It follows from this that the amount of ionic surfactants required to suppress maxima of similar sign is greater than that for those possessing dissimilar charges⁹.

Antweiler¹⁰ has unambiguously proved that the polarographic maxima of the first kind are due to tangential streaming of the solution with respect to the drop. The success of a maxima suppressor depends on its capability of curbing this streaming. Since the maxima in the present study lie on the negative side of the electrocapillary zero, the cationic surfactants will move right up to the mercury surface and the anionic ones are likely to move at a distance somewhere in the double layer. A cationic surfactant will prevent streaming more effectively as compared to an anionic one with identical hydrocarbon chain. This is supported by the fact that LPC is more effective than SLS, though both the surfactants have the same carbon chain length.

On the basis of M.S.P. values, the order of relative efficacies of cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactants in suppressing the negative maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols has been established as follows:

Cationic surfactants: LPC and CPC possess the same polar head but different carbon chain length. The following order exists for their efficacies: CPC > LPC. Thus, with the same polar head the efficacy of a cationic surfactant increases with the increase in carbon chain length.

In the case of CTAB and CDBAC which possess the same carbon chain length but different polar head, it is found that the former is more effective than the latter.

The efficacies of cationic surfactants are in the following order:

Anionic surfactants: In the case of Manoxol-IB and Manoxol-OT which possess the same polar head but different carbon chain lengths, it is found that the latter with longer carbon chain is more effective in suppressing these negative maxima. The efficacies of the anionic surfactants are in the following order:

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TABLE I—EFFECT OF IONIC AND NON-IONIC SURFACTANTS ON THE MAXIMA OF *o*-, *m*- AND *p*-NITROPHENOLS IN BR BUFFER OF pH 6.09

<i>ortho</i> -nitrophenol			<i>meta</i> -nitrophenol			<i>para</i> -nitrophenol		
[Surfactant] (M)	$-\frac{E_{max}}{V}$ (S.C.E.)	i_{max} μA	[Surfactant] (M)	$-\frac{E_{max}}{V}$ (S.C.E.)	i_{max} μA	[Surfactant] (M)	$-\frac{E_{max}}{V}$ (S.C.E.)	i_{max} μA
<i>Cationic</i>								
LPC × 10 ⁵								
0.0	0.58	88.16	0.0	0.61	61.60	0.0	0.65	85.88
0.2	0.56	72.20	0.5	0.58	42.70	0.5	0.63	64.60
0.7	0.54	47.88	0.8	0.57	31.50	0.8	0.60	47.88
1.0	0.51	40.28	1.0	0.56	28.00	1.0	0.59	38.76
2.0	0.50	31.16	1.5	0.54	23.10	1.4	0.58	29.64
3.0	0.375 ⁺	28.88*	2.3	0.430 ⁺	20.74*	2.0	0.482 ⁺	27.36*
CPC × 10 ⁵								
0.2	0.56	74.48	0.4	0.59	48.65	0.2	0.64	75.24
0.7	0.54	55.48	0.7	0.58	43.05	0.4	0.63	63.08
1.0	0.52	46.36	1.0	0.58	36.75	0.7	0.62	52.44
2.0	0.51	34.96	2.0	0.57 ⁺	24.50	1.0	0.60	41.04
3.0	0.390 ⁺	28.88*	3.0	0.490 ⁺	20.40*	2.0	0.481 ⁺	28.12*
OPB × 10 ⁵								
0.3	0.56	73.72	0.1	0.60	51.80	0.1	0.64	62.32
0.5	0.54	57.00	0.5	0.59	42.35	0.5	0.62	50.16
0.8	0.52	46.36	0.8	0.58	35.70	0.8	0.60	38.00
1.0	0.51	41.04	2.0	0.56	28.80	1.5	0.58	31.16
2.5	0.375 ⁺	29.64*	3.0	0.440 ⁺	20.74*	1.9	0.480 ⁺	27.36*
CDBAC × 10 ⁵								
0.2	0.56	72.96	0.2	0.60	49.00	0.2	0.64	64.60
0.4	0.54	53.96	0.5	0.58	39.20	0.5	0.62	47.88
0.6	0.52	42.56	0.8	0.57	30.10	0.8	0.60	39.52
1.0	0.50	31.92	1.0	0.56	24.50	1.0	0.58	33.44
2.0	0.380 ⁺	28.88*	2.5	0.435 ⁺	20.74*	1.4	0.480 ⁺	27.36*
CTAB × 10 ⁵								
0.2	0.56	69.16	0.2	0.60	56.00	0.2	0.64	65.36
0.4	0.54	53.96	0.4	0.59	47.60	0.4	0.62	53.20
0.6	0.52	41.80	0.8	0.58	36.75	0.6	0.60	42.56
1.0	0.50	32.68	2.0	0.56	21.70	0.8	0.58	33.44
2.0	0.385±	29.64*	3.0	0.440 ⁺	20.40*	1.1	0.482 ⁺	27.36*
<i>Anionic</i>								
DBS × 10 ⁴								
0.2	0.56	72.96	0.1	0.60	53.20	0.2	0.64	74.48
0.5	0.54	56.24	0.2	0.59	47.25	0.5	0.63	66.12
0.7	0.53	46.36	0.5	0.58	31.85	0.8	0.60	40.28
0.9	0.52	36.48	0.7	0.57	25.55	0.9	0.59	34.96
1.1	0.385 ⁺	28.88*	1.0	0.440 ⁺	20.40*	1.1	0.510 ⁺	28.12*
SLS × 10 ⁴								
0.2	0.56	62.32	0.1	0.60	52.50	0.1	0.64	76.00
0.4	0.54	47.12	0.2	0.58	36.75	0.2	0.62	64.60
0.5	0.52	41.04	0.4	0.56	25.90	0.4	0.61	48.64
0.6	0.50	34.20	0.5	0.56	22.40	0.6	0.60	34.20
0.7	0.375 ⁺	29.64*	0.6	0.497 ⁺	20.40*	0.8	0.500 ⁺	28.12*
Tergitol-7 × 10 ⁴								
0.3	0.56	69.92	0.1	0.60	52.50	0.3	0.63	66.88
0.5	0.54	51.68	0.3	0.59	42.00	0.5	0.61	48.64
0.7	0.52	42.56	0.5	0.58	33.25	0.7	0.60	40.24
0.9	0.50	24.96	0.7	0.57	26.25	0.9	0.59	23.44
1.2	0.377 ⁺	28.88*	1.0	0.440 ⁺	20.40*	1.2	0.500 ⁺	28.12*
Manoxol-OT × 10 ⁴								
0.09	0.54	72.96	0.2	0.60	47.76	0.2	0.64	69.16
0.40	0.52	53.96	0.4	0.58	39.90	0.4	0.63	60.04
0.60	0.50	45.60	0.6	0.57	35.00	0.6	0.62	50.16
0.90	0.48	30.40	1.2	0.56	22.40	1.1	0.60	31.92
1.20	0.375 ⁺	28.88*	1.6	0.435 ⁺	19.04*	1.3	0.492 ⁺	27.36*
Manoxol-IB × 10 ⁴								
0.9	0.54	62.32	0.1	0.60	47.60	0.01	0.63	72.96
1.6	0.52	53.20	0.5	0.59	38.50	0.07	0.62	62.32
2.5	0.50	44.34	1.0	0.58	31.50	0.50	0.61	47.12
3.0	0.48	34.96	2.0	0.56	22.75	1.20	0.60	31.92
4.0	0.400 ⁺	28.88*	3.2	0.430 ⁺	18.02*	1.60	0.500 ⁺	27.36*

(Table 1 Contd.)

Non-ionic								
**Triton X-100 × 10^a								
0.06	0.56	72.96	0.05	0.60	56.95	0.06	0.64	66.12
0.10	0.54	62.32	0.10	0.59	46.90	0.10	0.63	54.72
0.40	0.52	44.08	0.30	0.58	36.40	0.20	0.62	46.96
0.80	0.51	34.96	0.60	0.56	22.05	0.40	0.60	32.68
1.20	0.380 ⁺	29.64*	0.80	0.430 ⁺	20.40*	0.55	0.498 ⁺	27.36*
**Gelatin × 10^a								
0.2	0.56	79.04	0.2	0.60	49.35	0.2	0.64	76.76
0.6	0.54	64.60	0.5	0.58	43.40	0.5	0.62	63.84
1.0	0.53	56.24	1.0	0.57	36.05	1.0	0.61	45.60
3.0	0.52	34.96	2.0	0.56	23.45	2.0	0.60	31.92
4.4	0.375 ⁺	28.88*	3.0	0.440 ⁺	20.40*	2.5	0.500 ⁺	28.88*
**Decon-90 × 10^a								
0.5	0.56	76.00	0.5	0.60	42.35	0.5	0.64	75.24
1.0	0.55	63.08	0.8	0.59	32.20	1.0	0.62	60.04
2.0	0.53	43.32	1.0	0.58	28.35	2.0	0.61	44.84
3.0	0.52	34.96	2.0	0.56	22.75	3.0	0.60	33.44
4.5	0.378 ⁺	29.64*	3.0	0.430 ⁺	20.74*	4.0	0.500 ⁺	28.12*
Ethylidigol × 10^a								
0.2	0.56	78.28	0.2	0.58	48.60	1.0	0.63	68.40
0.7	0.52	55.36	0.7	0.56	40.95	2.0	0.61	59.96
2.0	0.48	48.64	2.0	0.54	34.65	3.0	0.58	41.04
6.0	0.42	31.16	6.0	0.50	21.35	4.0	0.56	34.96
8.0	0.355 ⁺	28.12*	8.0	0.430 ⁺	19.04*	5.5	0.470 ⁺	27.36*
2-Ethoxy ethanol × 10								
0.1	0.52	69.92	0.08	0.58	47.25	0.06	0.60	61.66
0.3	0.50	61.56	0.20	0.56	40.60	0.10	0.58	52.44
0.4	0.49	51.68	0.40	0.54	35.35	0.20	0.56	41.04
0.6	0.48	44.08	0.60	0.52	22.05	0.40	0.52	31.16
0.7	0.410 ⁺	28.88*	0.70	0.435 ⁺	19.04*	0.65	0.420 ⁺	27.36*

* Denotes the value of i_d
 + Denotes the value of E_{11}
 ** Concentrations expressed in percentage.

TABLE 2—M.S.P., S.S.C. AND C.M.C. VALUES FOR IONIC AND NON-IONIC SURFACTANTS FOR THE MAXIMA OF *o*-, *m*- AND *p*-NITROPHENOLS

Surfactant	<i>ortho</i> -nitrophenol			<i>meta</i> -nitrophenol			<i>para</i> -nitrophenol		
	M.S.P. (M)	S.S.C. (M)	C.M.C. (M)	M.S.P. (M)	S.S.C. (M)	C.M.C. (M)	M.S.P. (M)	S.S.C. (M)	C.M.C. (M)
Cationic	× 10 ⁵	× 10 ⁵	× 10 ⁵	× 10 ⁵	× 10 ⁵	× 10 ⁵	× 10 ⁵	× 10 ⁵	× 10 ⁵
LPC	2.34	4.89	10.00	2.26	5.31	8.00	1.58	6.24	10.00
GPC	2.14	5.82	7.00	2.20	7.76	7.00	1.48	5.43	7.00
CPB	2.44	4.78	5.00	2.45	4.26	5.00	1.78	2.09	5.00
CDBAC	1.27	3.38	6.00	2.16	4.47	5.00	1.20	3.02	8.00
CTAB	1.17	3.02	6.00	2.04	6.16	4.00	1.00	3.31	4.00
Anionic	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴
DBS	1.07	0.43	0.66	0.93	0.29	0.20	0.10	0.59	0.50
SLS	0.68	0.23	0.48	0.56	0.12	0.20	0.07	0.31	0.32
Tergitol-7	1.12	0.43	0.50	0.98	0.34	0.30	0.11	0.40	0.50
Manoxol-OT	1.14	0.28	0.54	1.51	0.38	0.60	0.13	0.48	0.46
Manoxol-IB	339.00	116.00	250.00	302.00	39.80	50.00	15.80	18.60	38.00
Non-ionic	× 10 ³	× 10 ³		× 10 ³	× 10 ³		× 10 ³	× 10 ³	
*Triton X-100	0.12	0.01		0.07	0.02		0.05	0.01	
*Gelatin	0.43	0.09		0.24	0.07		0.23	0.07	
*Decon-90	0.44	1.15		2.57	0.54		3.89	1.12	
Ethylidigol	7.08	1.23		7.50	0.77		5.97	1.78	
2-Ethoxy ethanol	69.70	34.60		67.40	20.40		63.00	79.40	

* Concentrations expressed in percentage.

Non-ionic surfactants : Non-ionic or amphoteric substances suppress maxima on the basis of preferential adsorption on the mercury drop. The efficacy of these suppressors depends upon the potential range of the maxima. Different non-ionic suppressors are adsorbed on the mercury drop to different extent at a given potential. The order of the efficacies is as follows :

Triton X-100 > Gelatin > Decon-90 > Ethyldigol
> 2-Ethoxy ethanol

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